

STORIES OF DEVOTION: A CASE STUDY OF FEMALE FOLLOWERS OF RADHA SOAMI

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Abstract

In this paper, we will explore the teachings and traditions of the organisation and a description of the cosmological model of Radha Soami and about their five dynamic regions, and a short idea about the lineage of the Dinod branch, and try to understand what their faiths and practices are and how followers internalise them and their instances of miracles. We use case studies to understand their stories of devotion and how their devotion creates a strong bond with their living God, i.e., spiritual guru or leader. We interviewed female followers of Radha Soami, and they shared their insights into miraculous instances, allowing us to understand the centrality of the spiritual leader, or guru. Complete devotion and submission to the guru are very much required in the organisation. In this paper we will also get the idea that family and society play a very important role for their motivations to join or attend the satsang and how their belief system helps them to connect with the divine energy through the devotion towards guru or their practice i.e. Surat Shabda yoga that is also considered as Sahaj yoga for the devotee and how the social media platform plays exceptional role in influencing the people and provide the cultural or salvation goods that people want in modern times.

Keywords: *Surat Shabad Yoga, Miracles, Cosmological model, Spiritual Guru*

There are numerous popular New Religious Movements worldwide. Radha Soami is one among them. Radha Soami is a Sant Mat movement, and it is more popular in the north-west part of India. It has many branches. We will not delve deeply into the definition of New Religious Movement; instead, we will explore the concept of satsang and its associated practices. For this paper, we have conducted in-depth interviews with followers of the Dinod Branch of Radha Soami. These Movements have institutions of their own; institutional features are one among them. These movements have elements from almost every religion, but the Hindu religion's elements are most prevalent in their nature, such as the tradition of a living

guru and meditation. According to Warriar (2003), these movements serve as ‘Hinduizing agents,’ promoting the nationalist ideology of Hindutva proponents. However, the current phenomenon involves avatar gurus, significant figures who establish institutional movements. This Movement was started by Sant Shiv Dayal Singh Ji in Dayal Bhag, Agra. He took initiation and inherited the Sant teachings from Tulsi Sahib of Hathras (1763– 1843), the author of Ghat Ramayana, a complex encyclopaedic work that presents a particular strain of late Sant thought, described by scholars as “ultraist” (Barthwal, 1936) and “esoteric” (Gold 1987; Juergensmeyer, 1991). Indian Tradition follows two Paths for Bhakti: one is Sagun Bhakti, i.e., Worshipping Gods in forms, for example, Shri Krishna, Lord Ram, etc.; the other is Nirgun Bhakti Path, i.e., worshipping God in a formless manner. Radha Soami follows the Nirgun Bhakti Path. They believed in the connectedness or union of the soul with divine energy through simple practices, such as Nam Japna or meditation. They also believed that a person, while fulfilling their societal duties, can attain salvation through the practice of Nam japna. “The origins of Radhasoami yoga are diverse and should be seen as the outcome of an extended historical evolution within the Sant tradition. Suratsabd-yoga, which incorporates a significant bhakti (devotional) element, was undoubtedly influenced by both Vaishnavas (devotees of Lord Vishnu) and Sufis.” (Callewaert,2011).

Centrality of Guru:

Guru plays the role of a bridge between the devotee and the Divine Energy. In this tradition, it primarily focuses on the disciples’ devotion to their guru. “The term ‘guru’ originates from two roots: ‘gu,’ signifying darkness or ignorance, and ‘ru,’ representing light or complete annihilation.” (Charpentier, 2010). “The Radha Soami faith comprises two primary components: guru bhakti, which refers to devotion to the guru, and Surat shabad yoga, which involves the union (yoga) of the spirit or soul entity (Surat) with the Divine sound or word (shabad)”. (Kakar, 1985). Through guru bhakti and the discipline of Surat Shabad yoga, one can attain a higher realm of consciousness. In the Radha Soami tradition, adherents believe in complete submission to the guru's wishes. The guru is regarded as a spiritual guide, and for followers, their guru holds a position akin to that of a deity. The guru is believed to have the power to liberate devotees from the cycle of transmigration and lead them toward salvation during their lifetime. According to tradition, a living guru can alleviate sorrow and illuminate the path for their followers. Guru is central in Sant Mat or new religious movements. “Gurus, believed to embody divinity, are worthy of worship and are sometimes regarded as equals to God.” (Charpentier, 2010). The Dinod branch of Radha Soami in Haryana is relatively new.

After the death of Seth Shiv Dayal Singh Ji, Saling Ram became the successor. After that, many branches had emerged. I got some insights into the lineage of the guru of Dinod Ashram. They have six gurus in total.

Lineage of gurus in Radha Soami, Dinod			
Guru number	Name	Birth Date	Passing Date
1 st	Shiv Dayal Singh	August 1818	June 1878
2 nd	Saling Ram	March 1829	December 1898
3 rd	Maharishi Shiv Brat Lal	February 1860	February 1939
4 th	Ram Singh Arman	September 1895	September 1976
5 th	Tarachand	August 1925	January 1997
6 th	Kanwar Saheb	March 1948	Present

One of the chief successors of Salingram ji was Shivbrat Singh ji, who established his ashram in Allahabad, Uttar Pradesh. After the initiation from Shivbrat Singh ji, Ram Singh ji was the main guru, and Shivbrat Singh ji made him the main guru of Haryana and Ram Singh was from Jui village of Haryana, but Ram Singh ji did not establish any ashram, and he lived his life like a hermit and did Satsang at people's homes in villages. The next guru, Tarachand ji, established the Haryana branch by taking initiation from the Radha Soami panth. Presently, the chief head of the Radha Soami Dinod branch is Kanwar Saheb Singh Maharaj. Kanwar Sahib Ji Maharaj was born on March 2, 1948, in the village of Dinod, Bhiwani district. Her mother's name is Smt. Muthari Devi's father's name is Ch. Surjaram Ji. His father left the world when he was just 4 years old. His mother was a follower of Sant Tarachand ji Maharaj. Kanwar ji was a teacher by profession and a regular attendee of his guru, Maharaj Tarachand ji's, satsang. From 1994, he became the servant of his guru and a disciple (beloved disciple) of Gurumukh, Tarachand ji, completely. "The guru-disciple relationship is characterized by a close and intimate connection based on mutual understanding and commitment." (Charpentier, 2010), and he also wrote many books, i.e., 'Radhasoami Naam Nijnam v Sada Ki Mukti', 'Jui Se Jahan', 'Pravachan Sangraha', and 'Satguru Prem'. On January 3, 1997, Tarachand ji handed over full responsibility to Kanwar ji. Soami Maharaj once said about the world and the devotion towards the Guru:

This world is perishable, and so are all worldly things.

The wise man is he who realizes the transitory and

illusory nature of this world and all things pertaining

to it, and makes the best use of this body by worshipping the Supreme Being, through bhajan and Simran.

He thus derives benefit from all that the Creator,

through His grace, has placed in the body, and takes that priceless jewel, the essence of all—the surat (the soul)—to its real abode.

Soami Ji Maharaj

Guru's Charisma still holds a very important aspect in the organisation. 'The lasting influence of Hindu-inspired faith movements (HIFMs) depends on three main factors: identifying followers, spreading the teachings, and establishing sacred spaces. Notably, the guru's charisma is centred within the ashram or retreat, serving as a pivotal point for cross-national dynamics of charisma dissemination and migration.' (Pandya, 2015). We are living in the post-modern era, but still, this charisma has not faded away. The charisma of gurus plays a central role in the emergence of Hindu-inspired faith movements (HIFMs). (Copley, 2000). 'This charisma is perpetuated and transformed through hagiographies, social memory, and oral practices'. (Srinivas 1999).

The term: Radha Soami

Once Soami ji Maharaj said that "The form of 'Radhasoami'... is without a limited description. To what could I compare it? It is beyond all means." Radhasoami faith follows a cosmological model. In this model, the upper layers of the cosmos are considered fine or subtle (sukshma), whereas the lower layers are seen as gross or coarse (sthula). The principle that the spiritual or finer aspects ascend, while the material or denser elements descend, is central to the entire Radhasoami belief system. "This fundamental concept is significant for the understanding of the self and is closely linked to the notion of the subtle body. The subtle self (surat) was originally a part (amś) of the Supreme Being (rādhāsvāmī), but at some point, it got separated, descended to the lower material realm, and was caught in the cycle of transmigration (caurāsī), thus forgetting its place of origin and its true identity" (Babb, 1986). The primary objective for humans is to seek their origin, which involves engaging in surat-shabad-yoga. This practice aims to merge the soul with the 'shabad' the original creative power of the Supreme Being from which the entire cosmos emerged. "The micro- and macrocosmological scheme is built on the assumption that the purification process of the soul always proceeds from the coarse, being "down here," to the subtle, being "up there" (Babb, 1986, p. 37). In Radha Soami Tradition, four grand regions of meditation play an important role in getting connected to Divine Power. After emerging from deep meditation (sunn samadhi), the Supreme Being generated a divine

sound current and brought forth five Grand Regions. The highest among these regions is known as Nirmal-Chaitanya-Desh, also referred to as the Peaceful Dynamic Region. In it are located Radha Soami's five regions, and these dynamics are the stages in the tradition. Its five "regions" constitute, in fact, five aspects of the Highest Being: satlok ("realm of being"), anāmī lok ("realm of the nameless"), alakh lok ("realm of the invisible"), agam lok ("realm of the inaccessible"), and rādhāsvāmī dhām ("realm of Rādhā soā mī̄") (Babb, 1986, pp. 38–40; Juergensmeyer 1991: 101–4). "The loftiest realms—Satlok (the ultimate abode of the soul) and the Supreme Being's domain (Rādhāsvāmī Dhām)—are accessible only to genuine Sants. Among them, Soami Ji himself attained the highest and most distant sphere, known as the "dhur," which represents the origin of all existence and the true abode of supreme Sants." (Sār Bacan Prose 1.7).⁴ According to the teachings of the Radha Soamis, this practice is divided into three parts. They are the following:

- (i) Sim ran (repetition of Nam): The practice of repeating a word or phrase is known as Simran. In Surat Shabad Yoga, Simran is the initial stage. It can be performed using fingers, tongue, throat, heart, or even the navel. However, the method of Simran that involves mindlessly counting rosary beads is regarded as a lesser form of the practice.
- (ii) Dhyān (contemplation of Guru): According to the teachings of the Radha Soami Faith, the second phase in Surat Shabad Yoga is Dhyān (contemplation). After gathering our focus at the third eye through Simran, it tends to disperse. To maintain concentration at that point, one should meditate on the luminous astral figure of one's Guru, which is believed to be present within the third eye.
- (iii) Bhajan (listening of Shabad): The third stage is Bhajan, which involves listening to the Anhad Shabad. Soami ji emphasizes that two elements are crucial for spiritual awakening and internal realization: (i) devotion to one's Guru, and (ii) listening to the Anhad Shabad.

The theology of the movement is encapsulated in the concept of surat shabad yoga, "the discipline of concentrating on the divine word through one's inner current" (Juergensmeyer, 1987). These realms are pristine spiritual dimensions filled with light, love, bliss, and eternal peace. They remain unaffected by dissolution. The Radha Soami faith has three facets that include a) High Moral Living, b) a Strict Lacto Vegetarian Diet. Does not promote Celibacy. According to Soami ji Maharaj, the Surat Shabad is the Sahaj Yoga that anyone can perform; this is the easiest method of meditation. The chamaktar or miracles are a crucial aspect of these

religious organizations. Miracles play a very significant role in shaping the belief system of the devotee: A miracle, in its current context, refers to an extraordinary event attributed to divine intervention. Despite appearing impossible according to existing scientific knowledge or laws, it still occurs. “In its ‘proper phase’, a miracle focuses on connecting the ‘involved’ with God(s)”. (Głaz, 2014). In his book “Miracles in Religion,” Anil Sarwal (1996) asserts that those who can perform astonishing miracles are often considered the most spiritually attuned. In simpler terms, charisma is closely associated with spiritual depth. A book written by Yujin Nagasawa about the little introduction of Miracles has classified miracles into three types:

- a) Material Miracles
- b) Biological Miracles
- c) Mental miracles can be classified into three further types: supernatural perception; control of immaterial beings, such as angels, ghosts, and spirits; and spiritual communication.

Even in this modern world, people who experience miracles and faith become so strong that it helps followers believe that everything that happens is due to the guru’s grace. We will see the miraculous instances of the followers and how they perceive them.

Covering the modern needs of the Market:

In 21st century, the religious movements have established their profound impact on the people, and the social media plays a very important role and they modified according to the modern need of the people, we have seen examples in the Radha Soami, they created a simple technique that everyone can follow, because of the today's demand and other one is their easy practices of meditation even without sitting in the meditative position one can attain salvation just withing repeating the Nam given by the group. Here, we can use Bourdieu’s concept of Faith Capital. In a secular context, religious decline leads to feelings of insecurity. These religious organisations step in with a faith package that includes faith capital and control over the cultural good of salvation. “These aspects harmoniously correspond with modernity, providing sought-after ‘new age faith products.’ Specifically, the ‘virtual’ online presence of Hindu-inspired faith movements (HIFMs) serves as an expansion strategy, resulting in a cyber-diaspora engagement with Hinduism.” (Lal, 1999). Based on N. Zaidman’s exploration of new age phenomena (2007), Hindu-inspired faith movements (HIFMs) resonate with the concept of a ‘global spiritual marketplace.’ In this context, salvation goods are evaluated based on the cultural values they embody. “Hindu-inspired faith movements (HIFMs) actively engage with media,

leading to a 'mediatization of religion' (Lövheim, 2011). In this context, HIFMs play a role as religious actors, contributing to the shaping of media and society."

I first visited their main headquarters, i.e., Dinod, a village in the Bhiwani district of Haryana, on Sunday. This is the premise where you can get direct darshan of the guru and receive his blessings. On weekends, followers are more numerous than on other days. This area is especially for meeting with guru and there are two group divided by the sevadar of the satsang premise one is for male and another is for female, after a short satsang around for 1 hour and everyone was there singing some spiritual songs and satsang finished with hand risen by every devotee and called Radha Soami after that one gets guru's darshan by standing in the queue. "Devotees eagerly seek the sacred vision (darsana) of their guru, believing it possesses healing abilities. Additionally, disciples are encouraged to channel their affectionate devotion toward the guru. In this light, Radhasoami can be understood as guru-bhakti." (Juergensmeyer 1987: 339-41). After that, followers go to the langar area to receive food, and there is a star temple located there, namely the former Sant Tarachand Samadhi, to seek their blessings (matha tekna). The samadh is a resting place for the remains of great religious patronage (Babb,1986). Blessings from the samadhi are of great importance to devotees; for them, it holds the same power as a living guru. Contact with them is the same as their contact with the supreme being, and it aids in achieving salvation from the sorrow and endlessly recurring deaths that are the lot of beings who inhabit this world (Babb, 1986). The building of the star temple is very beautiful, and Sant Tarachand was the founder of the Radha Soami Haryana branch. I approached a lady with a smiling face and greet her Radha Soami, I asked her about her journey in a subtle way, I talked her and she said that you can visit my home where I can give you all details about the Guru Maharaj, then very next day I visited her home which is in a village named Chirya in Charkhi Dadri district, she welcomed me very generously I talked to her, I heard that she was a very staunch follower of guru Maharaj. I have asked about her journey, why she joined, and why she continued to follow these traditions. She clearly mentioned to us that she finds great satisfaction after joining the Satsang. She and her friend were frequent visitors to Guru Maharaj during their youth; now, both are in their 70s, and they still continue to attend Satsang whenever they have the time. She said that during their young age, her husband, who is a doctor by profession, didn't let her go there, but she and her friend did attend satsang without telling their husband and in-laws. She said that we used to go in fear that someone might see us and catch us. We asked about miraculous instances, and she was very confident and said...

*“.....guru Maharaj performed so many miracles
that if you make the list then it would be short.*

Miracles started happening in my life the moment I started going to satsang....”

She said that right now I'm in my 70s and not in a condition to sit in meditation and Nam Japna. She gave us a vivid picture of the miraculous instances in her life. First, she told us that my husband's clinic was not going well at that time, and Maharaj visited (Charan pherna) the clinic. After that, my husband's clinic has been running smoothly. She said that one has to be very good to get Maharaj's Daya or mercy, and if the guru comes to your home, she simply says "Charan pherna" then everything becomes fine. At her house, Maharaj ji visited around 10 to 12 times, and in North India, there is a ceremony called "Bhaat Bharna"; even the guru has performed this ceremony for her. She simple said with great satisfaction that I got everything in my life what for but she regrated one thing, she said many years ago she was sitting in her meditative posture and performing nam japna practice somewhere around 3 or 4 am in the morning, suddenly she heard a voice from the sky and she saw her 4th guru Ram Singh Ji Maharaj and he said that you diligently performed your practices and now you have completed this journey do you want anything now on? She said that at that time, I had no idea what to ask for, and I should have said that I only wanted you and nothing else. But what I asked for, please make my son a doctor and fulfill his wish. She also added that when my son's got married, we also wanted a grandson then we went to guru ji and he gave us an apple after praying and then with grace of guru my grandson was born and happily living my life and guru ji gave me everything whatever I wanted for and I did everything to become a good human being and never did wrong to anyone and follow the path of Radha Soami. This story shows us that one's faith must be strong to follow the path of any religious organization. "The relationship is thereby mutually constituted and reciprocal, even as it demands the complete voluntary submission of the disciple to the guru's will" (Lucia, 2018, p. 980).

Next day we went to the Satsang again we have talked to another lady that is belong to Dinod village itself we approached the lady during langar service, I was sitting behind her, then with a smiling face I started talking to her that, guru's grace is very much important for me and I'm newly joined member of the Satsang, she said that you are in a right place, she started telling her story about her journey, she has a very unique story, The lady is somewhere around in her 50's and living with her mother-in-law, one daughter-in-law and two adopted grandchildren.

She is illiterate and lives below the poverty line. When we asked her about her journey towards Radha Soami, she said she has a strong faith in it. She said that

“... *guru Maharaj did that thing that no one could do...*”

When we asked what he did, she told us that around 8 to 10 years ago our buffalo's tail was cut off, sometimes its ears were cut off I lost my son during that instances and I was sure that someone used to do black magic(*tuna totka*) and our family life was shattered and did everything but nothing worked and I almost lost everything and my financial conditions were worst then someone from the village told me about Maharaj ji and then I went there and after naam initiation nothing happened like that and now we have a buffalo and everything is perfect. She also added some more instances that strengthened her belief in the satsang. Her grandson kept seeing a woman, a *pitra* (ghost), and was always scared of her. Then she took her grandson to the satsang, and he also took Naam and always wore a Maharaj ji pendant around his neck. After that, his problem was completely resolved. We also spoke with his grandson about this instance, and he shared with us the same information his grandmother had told us. She said that if one follows the path of the guru, things like *kala jadu* (black magic) and *akal maut* (sudden death) will not occur in anyone's home. This is their strong belief that makes it possible for them to believe in their god.

Another story we have heard is from a lady in her 40s who is a graduate and works with an Anganwadi. When we interviewed her about her journey then she said my knee pain was completely resolved after going there and one incident that made her belief stronger towards the guru was that she was travelling in a car with her whole family his two son and his husband and they met with an accident and she said that she had clearly seen the vision of guru and nothing happened and we were all safe and not even a simple bruise was there and she thanked guru for his whole life and next day they went for satsang his guru showed them bruises all over his stomach and waist and he said that suddenly my attention has gone towards my bhaktas that somewhere sitting in the satsang and she said that guru ji took their troubles on himself that's why we are safe now. Then we asked her about how much meditation and *nam japana* she is doing everyday she said that not that much but my guru's *kripa* or grace is there and this is the important thing for us and I also talked to other members of her family and they all told me that they all following the satsang tradition because of this mother or grandmother, here we can clearly see that women plays very important role in influencing their children's religious behaviour. We can cite some previous studies on her. Female followers have a very vital role in encouraging their family members to follow the organisation. In the case study, it is clearly

evident that the women of the family helped to instill a belief in miracles, and they shared their stories with other family members as well. The role of women in religion (including its evolution) is significant and has been duly recognized by previous scholars. These authors have explicitly noted that mothers often share stories of God(s), Prophets, and miracles with their children, often alongside milk or as bedtime tales. (Sarwal, 1996; Leirvik, 2010). “This is noted as an independent chain of transmission paralleling the religious education given by the clergy or the society in general” (Leirvik, 2010).

We can see that how the religious organisation’s belief system impacts the followers. We can here quote that exactly fulfills the criteria of this. Movements of this kind strive to create culturally meaningful theologies that impact behaviours, worldviews, and ways of life (Sutherland et al., 1988). Guided by a charismatic leader, the central focus lies in convincing people of the potential improvement of human nature in the present moment. Much of the theoretical framework supporting this perspective is rooted in the belief that each individual possesses divine qualities. According to Ludwig Feuerbach, the focus here is not on God as an external entity, but rather on the God who exists within and for each individual. The true significance of this concept lies in how it shapes our understanding of human existence.” The boundary between faith and knowledge becomes less distinct, resembling a Durkheimian connection between the sacred and the profane” (Copley, 2000)

Conclusion:

Our case studies have provided insight into the guru and how followers perceive their messages and miraculous instances. Until now, Guru’s charisma has played a very crucial role in these religious organisations. They influenced people in many ways. Role plays by the family or societal conditions play a crucial role in developing a strong belief system towards the organisation. Social media platforms and other internet activities have also helped the organisation create and develop a strong belief system towards the guru. The cosmological model of the Radha Soami is closely tied to the meditation technique; this model must be understood if a person wishes to follow the path of spirituality through Surat Shabad Yoga. However, in the present day, people seek simple yet effective techniques; thus, methods are modified to meet the demands of the time and fulfill the needs of their followers. Social media has a vital role in this. Social media conveys the message about the organisation's practices and charismatic instances, as well as other market-supported elements, which makes followers believe in the organisation. Female followers have a significant influence on their family, especially over their children, and thus have developed their spiritual beliefs towards their

beloved Guru. Social conditions of the person, like how their socialization is done in their families, how their society in which they live teaches them, and how the person wants to live their life, i.e., their mental satisfaction, spiritual upliftment, or life goals, lead them to believe in these charismatic personalities and follow a certain path to live his or her life.

References

- Babb, L. A. (1986). *Redemptive encounters: Three modern styles in the Hindu tradition*. Oxford University Press. New Delhi
- Babb, L. A. (1986). *Redemptive encounters: Three modern styles in the Hindu tradition*.
- Barthwal, P. D. (1936). *The Nirguna school of Hindi poetry: An exposition of medieval Indian Santa mysticism*. Indian Book Shop. Benares
- Callewaert, W. A. (2011). Sants. In K. A. Jacobsen (Ed.), *Brill's Encyclopedia of Hinduism* (Vol. 3, pp. 532-545). Brill.
- Charpentier, M.-T. (2010). *Indian female gurus in contemporary Hinduism: A study of central aspects and expressions of their religious leadership [Doctoral dissertation, Åbo Akademi University]*.
- Copeman, J., & Ikegame, A. (2012). *The guru in South Asia: New interdisciplinary perspectives*. Routledge.
- Copley, A. (2000). *Gurus and their followers*. Oxford University Press. New Delhi
- Glaz, S. (2014). Characteristics of extraordinary religious phenomena accompanying the Christian religious experience—Reflection. *Religions*, 5, 1146-1160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel5041146>
- Gold, D. (1987). *The Lord as Guru: Hindi Sants in North Indian tradition*. Oxford University Press. New York
- Gold, D. (2015). The Hindi Sant's two yogic paths to a formless Lord. In H. Eifring (Ed.), *Meditation and culture: The interplay of practice and context* (pp. 131-146). Bloomsbury Academic.
- Juergensmeyer, M. (1987). The Radhasoami revival of the Sant tradition. In K. Schomer & W. H. McLeod (Eds.), *The Sants: Studies in a devotional tradition of India* (pp. 329-355). University of California, Berkeley Religious Studies Series.
- Juergensmeyer, M. (1991). *Radhasoami reality: The logic of a modern faith*. Princeton University Press.
- Kakar, S. (1985). Psychoanalysis and Religious Healing: Siblings or Strangers? *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, 53(4), 841-851.
- Lal, V. (1999). The politics of history on the Internet: Cyber diasporic Hinduism and the North American Hindu diaspora. *Diaspora*, 8(2), 137-172.
- Leirvik, O. (2010). *Images of Jesus Christ in Islam* (2nd ed.). Bloomsbury Publishing Plc. Available at: www.bloomsbury.com
- Lövheim, M. (2011). Mediatisation of religion: A critical appraisal. *Culture and Religion*, 12(2), 153-166.
- Lucia, A. J. (2018). Guru sex: Charisma, proxemic desire, and the haptic logics of the guru-disciple relationship. *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, 86(4), 953-988. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jaarel/lfy025>
- Nagasawa, Y. (2017). *Miracles: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press. United Kingdom
- Pandya, S. (2013). Charisma, routinisation, and institution building: Hindu-inspired faith movements in contemporary India. *Sociological Bulletin*.
- Pandya, S. P. (2018). *Faith movements and social transformation: Guru charisma in contemporary India*. Springer Nature Singapore.
- Sarwal, A. (1996). *Miracles in religion: A study of the miraculous in religion in context of the Bahá'í Faith*. Royale Publishers, Lucknow, India.

- Soamiji Maharaj. (1970). *Sar Bachan Radhasoami Poetry* (S.D. Maheshwari, Trans.). Soami Bagh, Agra: Radhasoami Satsang.
- Soamiji Maharaj. (2018). *Sar Bachan Radhasoami Prose*. Soami Bagh Translation. [Online]. Available: Archive.org.
- Srinivas, S. (1999). *Sai Baba: The double utilisation of written and oral traditions in a modern South Asian religious movement*. *Diogenes*, 47(3), 88-99.
- Sutherland, S., Clarke, P., & Hardy, F. (1988). *Introduction*. In S. Sutherland, L. Holden, P. Clarke, & F. Hardy (Eds.), *The world's religions* (pp. 16-39). Routledge. London
- Warrier, M. (2003). *The Seva ethic and the spirit of institution building in the Mata Amritanandamayi Mission*. In A. Copley (Ed.), *Hinduism in public and private* (pp. 254-289). Oxford University Press.
- Zaidman, N. (2000). *The integration of Indian immigrants to temples run by North Americans*. *Social Compass*, 47(2), 205-219.
- Zaidman, N. (2007). *New age products in local and global contexts*. *Culture and Religion*, 8(3), 255-270.